

Government Capabilities for the Twin Transition

A Multilevel Framework Based on a Narrative Literature Review

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Abstract

Two different external socio-technical developments – the (ecological) sustainability transition and the digital transition – require governments to build the capability to respond and lead the way. While there is extensive literature on the sustainable transition and on the digital transition, so far limited attention has been paid to the interconnectedness of these transitions. Furthermore, a thorough understanding of the government capabilities needed to make this ‘twin transition’ work, is lacking. In this study, we aim to bring these separate strands of literature together to identify the required government capabilities for the twin transition. Based on a narrative literature review, we identify institutional, organizational and individual capabilities and highlight interfaces between these levels. We conducted an exploratory test of the value of the framework in two Dutch cities. Our research results in a multilevel conceptual framework of government capabilities for the twin transition. This framework enables governments to strategically develop their capabilities and provides a basis for further academic research on this topic.

1. Introduction

While the sustainability transition and the digital transition have often been seen as separate challenges, their interconnectedness is currently increasingly emphasized (Meijer, 2024). The twin transition has been identified as a key area of research by the European Union with the following message in the report ‘Toward a green and digital future’: “To unlock their potential and to prevent negative effects, the green and digital transitions require a proactive and integrated management,” (Muench et al., 2022: iv). Both challenges – safeguarding the planet and domesticating technological innovation – have been extensively discussed but in separate strands of academic literature (Meijer, 2024). Building upon both strands of literature, this paper maps the capabilities that governments need to tackle the challenges of the twin transition.

The first building block for this paper is the literature on the role of government in the sustainability transition. Since the Brundland Report in 1987, the sustainability transition has dominated in societal and academic debates on key societal challenges. Strong overviews of the development of academic thinking about the sustainability transition are provided by Caradonna (2017) and Redclift & Springett (2015). A broader and narrower perspective on the sustainability transition can be distinguished: the broader perspective focuses on social, economic and ecological sustainability whereas the narrower perspective only focuses on ecological sustainability (Purvis et al, 2019). In line with the European Union's focus on a 'green and digital future', this paper applies the narrow perspective and focuses mostly on ecological sustainability. The literature on transition studies has elaborated what this challenge means for institutional change in society in general and the role of government more specifically (Zolfagharian et al., 2019). More recent work extensively discusses how governments need to adapt to be able to realize key transition tasks has been (Blohm, 2021; Braams et al., 2021).

The second building block for this paper is the – more recent – literature on the digital transition of government. While there has been much attention for the 'information revolution', the 'data revolution' and now the 'AI revolution', only more recently these changes have been conceptualized as a 'digital transition'. The digital transition is a fundamental change process enabled by digital technologies that aims to bring radical improvement and innovation to society (Westerman et al., 2014; Vial, 2019). Specifically for governments, the digital transition is both an external challenge (Van Dijck, 2020) – how to respond to new challenges such as exploitation of platform workers, fake news and online attacks? – and an internal challenge – how to use the technologies to strengthen government effectiveness, efficiency and legitimacy (Mergel et al., 2019)? – which require different responses and interventions from governments (Meijer, 2025). The literature on the digital transition of government is currently rapid expanding (Mergel et al., 2019; Ahn, & Chen, 2022; Yang and Albitar, 2024).

While the literature on the role of government in the sustainability transition is enormous and the literature on the digital transition of government is rapidly expanding, the academic literature on the connections between the two transitions is limited and fragmented. Several publications, especially on smart cities, highlight possible synergies and argue more generally that digital transition can provide solutions to support sustainability efforts. For example, big data analytics, social media and AI technologies can help to implement sustainability solutions (Rosário & Dias, 2022). Other studies point out the challenges of the twin transition. Linkov et al. (2018) stress that big data promises to drive growth and contribute to the realization of the SDGs but also creates new types of vulnerabilities for cyber-attacks and power imbalances. In addition, the authors stress that artificial intelligence provides the promise of better decision-making about sustainability issues but also generates a host of (ethical) risks.

In sum, the urgency of governing the connections between the transitions is highlighted but, apart from the general requirements of the European Union (Muench et al., 2022), an understanding of government capabilities for the twin transition work is lacking. In this study, we combine the literature on the sustainability and digital transitions to identify the government capabilities needed to govern the twin transition. Based on a narrative literature review and an exploratory empirical test, we develop an academically and societally relevant framework for mapping governments' institutional, organizational and individual capabilities.

2. Theoretical background: multilevel framework

The basis for our narrative literature review is a conceptualization of 'government capability' as a multilevel concept. Polidano (2000: 808) defines the related concept capacity as "the ability of an organization to act effectively on a sustained basis in pursuit of its objectives". He distinguishes the "freedom to take decisions, its ability to take informed decisions, and its ability to have those decisions implemented" as core components (Polidano, 2000: 808). Wu et al. (2015) provide a more concrete definition of capability in the context of public policy as a set of skills, competences, resources, and

institutional arrangements and capabilities necessary to perform public policy functions. Following Piening's (2012: 213) literature review, we define a government capability as a collection of routines to execute and coordinate the different tasks required to perform an activity. Building on the work of Polidano (2000), Wu et al. (2015), Kattel (2022), Kattel et al. (2025) and Loorbach (2009), we identify government capabilities connected to institutions, organizations and individuals. These three levels form the basis of our conceptual framework and have been used as a structure for the narrative review.

The institutional level primarily deals with societal and political debate for example “vision development, strategic discussions, long term goal formulation, collective goal and norm setting, and long-term anticipation” (Loorbach 2009: 168-169). Institutional capabilities express the ability of government to write the rules of the game (Polidano, 2008). This concerns rules for use of digital technologies and policies for the sustainability transition. Long term governance often doesn't have an institutionalized place in regular policy making according to Loorbach (2009: 169) due to the short-term political cycles. At these institutional levels, it is important to integrate or institutionalize long-term governance activities as a fundamentally necessary element of policymaking for sustainable development. (Loorbach 2009)

Organizational capabilities concern the ability to execute organizational functions such as developing policy, programs, rules and regulations; managing infrastructure and organizational networks and coalitions; and carrying out decisions and enforce rules (Loorbach 2009; Polidano 2000). Activities are focused on realizing goals within a specific context. In this line, Mayne et al. (2019) refer to collaborative capability that inheres the breadth as well as the depth of cross-silo, cross-sector, and state-society relationships that public-sector organizations cultivate and leverage to address public problems. Organizational fragmentation in terms of different government departments might be a barrier for realizing long-term policies at the organizational level (Loorbach 2009).

Individual capabilities concern the skills and practices of individual employees that are needed to enact organizational ambitions. Thus, this set of capabilities refers to the human

resources of organizations that are needed to implement the work. Activities at this level are often driven by individual ambitions and skills. Hence, these capabilities are manifest both in the skills and knowledge of public-sector personnel and in their habituated working practices and behaviors within organizations (Mayne 2019).

The three levels lead to a multilevel framework for the identification of government capabilities for the twin transition: (1) the societal position of a government and its capability to institutionalize long term legitimate policy making and activities for the twin transition, (2) the capability focused on the translation of governmental ambitions into programs, policies and structures and (3) the capability to translate the strategy and tactics into requirements for (individual) skills and motivations to execute tasks in government organizations (see also the OECD-report by Willems & Baumert (2003) for a similar approach). To identify the capabilities for the twin transition in the academic and grey literature, we use the table below as a heuristic framework (see Table 1).

INSERT TABLE 1

3. Methodology: narrative review and explorative empirical test

Considering the emerging and cross-disciplinary nature of the twin transition we conducted a narrative review. Compared to a scoping review focused on mapping key concepts (Horsley 2019), or an integrative review focused on reviewing, critiquing and integrating literature (Torraco 2016), a narrative review allows us to review and investigate what is already known regarding capabilities for the twin transition, (Bryman, 2016; Chaney, 2021; Horsley 2019). Since the twin transition is an emerging concept, a systematic review with a narrow focus and aimed at collating all empirical evidence does not grasp the aim of this study. Narrative reviews on the other hand, are suitable for recognizing theories and frames of knowledge. Our goal was not to include all eligible research findings, perspectives and angles available. Our aim, however, was to conduct a wider exploration and gain insight into core publications as a basis for a conceptualization of the three levels of the multilevel framework. Therefore, a narrative review proved to be a suitable method (Sukhera, 2022).

At the same time, we acknowledge that narrative reviews have some limitations regarding reproducibility and transparency (Collins and Fauser 2005). Therefore, we followed rigorous narrative review guidelines (Sukhera, 2022).

The structured narrative review was carried out in four steps in 2023 and 2024. First, we conducted a *general* search on the twin transition, i.e. the combination of the sustainable transition and the digital transition in the context of public administration in Google Scholar, Scopus and Web of Science. As current research regarding the twin transition is limited, the approximately 20 found papers proved not to be sufficient to serve as the foundation for the multilevel framework. Therefore, second, we performed a *specific* search in the databases Scopus and Web of Science on each level of the multilevel framework for the sustainability transition as well as for the digital transition in the context of public administration, resulting in additional 45 papers. Third, an *additional* search was conducted to identify a small number of core publications in either the digital or sustainability domain to be able to identify capabilities at each level for both transitions. In this stage, we used snowballing where appropriate to capture relevant studies. Finally, we analyzed relevant policy papers such as the already mentioned JRC-report on the twin transition (Muench et al., 2022) and an EU-report about the impact of the twin transition on the labor market and the workplace (Bednorz et al., 2022).

For our searches on the ‘twin transition’, the ‘sustainability transition’ and the ‘digital transition, we used a combination of the search terms (public or government) ‘capabilities’, ‘capabilities’, ‘transition’ and ‘transformation’. We included both peer-reviewed papers as well as conference papers and book chapters and policy papers. The abstracts were scanned on relevance, and relevant papers were fully read and categorized by the researchers based on level and capability. To avoid researcher bias the review process consisted of regular meetings between the authors to reflect on the selection process and interpretation of the found articles in relation to our multilevel model (Sukhera 2020). The analysis focused on identifying shared conceptualizations of the three levels of the multilevel model. The analysis resulted in an initial conceptual model of government capabilities for the twin transition for each level: institutional, organizational and individual. Furthermore, based

on our analysis, we chose to consistently use the term ‘digital transition’ instead of ‘digital transformation’ because transition aligns with the term “twin transition”. Even though transition and transformation are often used interchangeable we do recognize that these concepts are not exactly the same (Hölscher et al 2018). However, for clarity and readability purposes, we use one term in this study. Hence, when we refer to “digital transition,” we build upon both digital transition and digital transformation scholarship.

To explore the value of this framework and to refine it, we conducted empirical research in two local governments in the Netherlands. We explored the framework’s usefulness for government organizations by first assessing current strengths and weaknesses in terms of the capabilities for the twin transition and second identifying courses of action for strengthening this capability. In one local government, we conducted 7 interviews with local civil servants and a workshop with 4 participants. In the other, we conducted 11 interviews and held a workshop with 9 participants. Respondents and participants in the workshop are either involved in the sustainability transition, digital transition, or the intersection between the two. The goal of the interviews and workshops was to assess the value of the framework by testing whether the framework could help to identify weaknesses in their current approaches and actions for improving government capabilities.

4 Findings

4.1 Capabilities for the twin transition

4.1.1. Institutional capabilities

In the literature we found a limited number of publications focused on the institutional capability for realizing the twin transition. Those publications are mainly related to the international and national level that might influence government strategic capability. To illustrate, Medaglia, Misaruca and Aquara (2021) investigated the link between digital government and the sustainable development goals through a systematic literature review and conclude that some relations have been investigated but overall, our academic knowledge on this relation is limited. In a more general review of the link between

digitalization and sustainability, Gouvea et al. (2018) show convincing support for a positive relation between a country's use of information and communication technologies and its environmental sustainability. Their study, however, does not provide information about how this is related to government capabilities.

In the European Union, the need to work on policy capability as a strategic capability has been highlighted through the recent policy paper on the twin transition (Muench et al., 2022). In parallel, policymakers in the United Nations (UN) and Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) are also examining the original sustainability policy concepts from the Brundtland Report through the lens of digitalization (Linkov et al., 2018). Linkov et al. (2018) develop this idea for the policy capability further and identify 'adaptive governance' as the capability that is needed for the twin transition or, in their own words, 'a sustainable digital world'. Adaptive governance is an approach that builds upon three governance approaches – laissez-faire, precautionary and stewardship – and connects these to three digitalization fields – big data, artificial intelligence and distributed ledgers – to realize digital sustainability – defined as economic, social and environmental sustainability. As they formulate it: 'Given the governing authorities and strategies taken by a given government, adaptability is needed to iteratively address adversarial threats related to digital sustainability as framed by the SDGs' (Linkov et al., 2018: 6). It appears, however, that the capabilities to develop green and digital solutions differ across European countries (Bachtrögler-Unger et al., 2023).

4.1.2 Organizational capabilities

We found some articles that provide a basis for organizational capability for the twin transition in the literature on public sector innovation. Important work by Kattel et al. (2022) emphasizes that innovation – referring to Mazzucato's entrepreneurial state – requires a strong bureaucracy. They emphasize that governments drive innovation, shape markets and steer inclusive green innovation. However, in the literature strand on public sector innovation, specific attention for the twin transition appears to be missing.

The internal aspect of the twin transition – using ICTs to make the organization more sustainable – has gained attention through research that delved into organizational rules or working principles of government organizations. To illustrate, Haley (2017) argues that working principles can spur sustainability by effectively implementing technology-specific policies. One of these working principles concerns creating a comprehensive outlook, so that coordination across various government or organization departments is fostered (Haley, 2017). Other principles concern accountability and competence, as well as more external-oriented principles. This external aspect of the twin transition – using digital technologies to make society more sustainable – is increasingly being emphasized as well. For example, Haley et al. (2017) argue how embeddedness in collaborative arrangements can help foster the twin transition.

Further, Haley et al. (2017) highlight room for exploration and experimenting is important. Within experimentation processes, moreover, flexibility appears crucial. If a pilot shows little promise, it is important to cancel these. To achieve this flexibility, it could be argued experiments are provided a certain level of independence from short-term political pressure and dynamics, for example in niches. This can, however, challenge political and hierarchical control.

4.1.3 Individual capabilities

Current research that explores individual capabilities for realizing the twin transition is scarce. However, Cordella et al. (2024) argue that digital skills from civil servants and public administrators are necessary facilitators in designing, implementing and managing policies regarding the digital transition that aim to achieve SDGs. The importance of individual competences is acknowledged for the twin transition as well (Haley et al., 2017).

Not only individual skills, but also individual perceptions are further examined in relation to the twin transition. To illustrate, Brenner & Hartl (2021) investigate how different actors perceive the interrelationship between digitalization and sustainability with the aim of understanding how, for example, policymakers and managers act in response to the twin transition. The authors distinguish four frames, of which two are neutral, whereas the other

two indicate a negative and a positive connotation. This research elaborates on insights from both framing theory and social representations theory, and therefore, the authors put emphasis on perceptions instead of capabilities. Other research that focuses on attitude and behavior regarding the transition towards a circular economy is focused on society instead of civil servants (Voukkali et al., 2023).

More general notions about capabilities of civil servants add to the analysis of the individual capabilities. A key argument from the literature is that individual servants do not need to have all the capabilities related to the two transitions, but they should be able to forge fruitful connections at the individual level. Schot et al. (2000) refer to this as collaborative professionalism: professionals should not only master their own field but also be able to connect their field to other fields. This can mean that digital experts need to acquire the capability to work with sustainability experts when making technological choices about digital technology. In addition, Kattel et al. (2022) emphasize that civil servants sometimes need to be ‘bureaucracy hackers’ who revolutionize government organizations from the inside by challenging existing bureaucratic routines and creating room for innovation.

4.2 Capabilities for the sustainability transition

4.2.1. Institutional capabilities

While there is limited discussion on institutional government capabilities for the twin transition, for the sustainability transition, there is a lively discussion on the government capabilities that are needed to tackle societal challenges and fulfill societal expectations. Regarding a sustainable planet, there is relative consensus on what the goals and expectations are that need to be fulfilled. In, 1987, the Brundtland Report provided the following definition that is still often used to indicate what the goal is of the sustainability transition: ‘Sustainable Development is the development that satisfies the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.’ (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987, par. 27).

The government interventions that are needed for the sustainability transition are widely debated (for overviews: Kraft, 2017; Russel & Kirsop-Taylor, 2022). These overviews both discuss the variety in key issues (e.g., climate change policies, biodiversity policies) and the various general issues for sustainable development policies (policy integration, policy instruments, collaborative governance). We would like to highlight two specific approaches here that have gained much traction in government and academic debates. A key approach for understanding this capability is transition management (Loorbach, 2010; Braams et al. 2022) which highlights how policymakers can shape the sustainability transition. Based on an analysis of many publications on transition management, Braams et al. (2022) have distilled five government tasks: give direction, support governance, support the new, destabilize the unsustainable and develop internal capabilities and structures. The key premise in this literature is that government policies are needed to radically transform current patterns. In parallel, an approach highlighting the need to work focused on these challenges is mission-oriented innovation (Mazzucato, 2018). This literature emphasizes the need for long-term government commitment and a clear focus. Mazzucato (2018: 810): ‘Missions should be broad enough to engage the public and attract cross-sectoral investment and remain focused enough to involve industry and achieve measurable success. By setting the direction for a solution, missions do not specify how to achieve success. Rather, they stimulate the development of a range of different solutions to achieve the objective. As such, a mission can make a significant and concrete contribution to meeting Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) or Societal Challenge.’ The work of Blohm (2021) further emphasizes the importance of mission-oriented innovation as setting up ‘the right political framework’ and developing long-term goals to enable strategic planning are underpinned as crucial aspects to create enabling environments.

In addition, there is substantive discussion about the type of collaboration between governments that is needed to realize the sustainability transition. The key institution is the United Nations and global collaboration is being discussed at United National Climate Change Conferences (COP). The Sustainable Development Goals are an institution created to facilitate these forms of global action and can even be labelled as ‘governance through

goals' (Kanie & Bierman, 2017): the idea is that jointly formulated goals will help to coordinate the global public and private action that is needed to realize the sustainability transition. Although collaboration is employed to foster collective action regarding the sustainability transition, McAllister & Taylor (2015) state that partnerships can also add complexity as it can generate conflict with other institutional objectives.

There is a debate on the new government position needed to realize the sustainability transition and how it can be legitimized. Various proposals have been made for innovating democracy to enhance its focus on the sustainability transition which emphasize the role of future generations and of non-human actors (Beckman, 2008; Thompson, 2010; Latour, 2017). The basic problem analysis is that current democratic arrangements emphasize the preferences of current human actors and therefore may not result in broad support for transition policies. New arrangements could shift the balance and therefore strengthen the legitimacy of transition policies. Recent work has highlighted the need to develop a new legitimizing rationale for transformative government (Braams et al., 2021). Braams et al. (2021) highlight how we need a new form of government legitimation – transformative government – as a basis for directing the actions and decisions of government at all levels towards the (long term) sustainability transition.

4.2.2 Organizational capabilities

The role policymakers and public authorities can play regarding the sustainability transition is increasingly emphasized in the literature (Farla et al., 2012). To illustrate, Lee (2023) specifically examines strategy implementation regarding sustainability in local governments. The author finds that the necessary degree of coordination, commitment, human resources, and financial resources differs across (different types of) local governments. Furthermore, Strumińska-Kutra et al. (2023) provide insights into organizational infrastructures that support energy transition agendas by developing propositions regarding internal organizational processes for the institutionalization of sustainable transition arrangements. The authors distinguish, for example, financial resources, institutional entrepreneurs, and innovative leadership in this regard.

As for the internal aspects of the sustainability transition, there is attention for the implementation capability, which concerns the reduction of the organization's environmental costs, for example by gathering insights regarding green insights. Adams et al. (2014) focus on the use of sustainable performance measures in the public sector as an operational activity. The literature on green organizations is mostly generic in nature (Green et al., 2000) and, as far as we could find, few publications specifically focus on government organizations. Green et al. (2000) analyze both public and private sector organizations and emphasize the need for organizations to focus on environmental sustainability in their purchasing, consumption and innovation. They conclude that the green organization is an organization that focuses on low use of energy, limited use of resources, a focus on recycling, limiting food waste, etc. For these efforts, there are no differences between public and private organizations. Some other studies focus on the topic of government procurement (Blome et al., 2014; Vejaratnam et al., 2020).

Furthermore, a whole body of literature addresses what government needs to do to contribute to the sustainable transition by collaborating with a variety of profit and non-profit organizations. Specifically, Pinz et al. (2021) conducted a systematic literature review on business as well as public administration literature to elaborate on whether empirical evidence indicates that public-private partnerships (PPPs) can support the accomplishment of sustainability objectives. The authors find that several success factors are crucial to accomplish sustainability-related objectives through PPPs, such as political and regulatory frameworks within initial conditions, planning and community consultation within process-factors, and defined responsibilities within an appropriate governance structure (Pinz et al., 2021).

4.2.3 Individual capabilities

A stream of publications addresses the question of employee green behavior (EGB) and how this can be stimulated. Ones and Dilchert (2012) identify with five categories of EGB: (1) working sustainably, (2) conserving resources, (3) influencing others, (4) taking initiative, and (5) avoiding harm. Unsworth et al. (2021) present a theoretical analysis of Employee Green Behavior (EGB) and stress that this is shaped by an interaction between

individual and organizational factors. Since not all individuals have the same attitude towards environmental sustainability, a diversity in approaches is needed to stimulate the various employees. To stimulate EGB, Green HRM is increasingly discussed in the literature. Rani & Mishra (2014: 3633): ‘Green HRM means using every employee interface in such a manner in order to promote and maintain sustainable business practices as well as creating awareness, which in turn, helps organizations to operate in an environmentally sustainable fashion.’

The attitude of civil servants towards the sustainability transition is addressed in a study by Stritch & Christensen (2014) on the link between organizational commitment and public service motives and public employees’ workplace eco-initiatives. On the basis of a study in a large city in the US, they find that connectedness to nature, organizational commitment, and public service motivation are significant predictors of eco-initiative in the public workplace. In addition, Alzgoool (2019) stresses that green HRM – human resource management directed at stimulating green behavior – plays an important role in stimulating employees to have a positive attitude towards green values.

The skills of civil servants for realizing the sustainability transition are discussed in empirical studies by Braams et al. (2023). They emphasize that civil servants need to have the organizational astuteness to react to contestation of efforts to realize the sustainability transition and to be able to drive the transition forward. These skills – and attitudes – are quite different from the traditional skills and attitudes of civil servants that emphasize legality and obedience. Moreover, Bianchi (2020) argues that sustainability competences should and could be embedded in any job to spur the sustainability transition, while key competences could be related to sustainability-related jobs.

4.3 Capabilities for the digital transition

4.3.1. Institutional capabilities

For the digital transition, the societal expectations are extensively debated. In the literature, many undesirable outcomes have been highlighted such as dehumanization (Nissenbaum

& Walker, 1998), big tech control (Alford, 2021), misinformation (Fowler-Watt & McDougall, 2022) and massive surveillance (Wood and Monahan, 2019). Various authors warn for technocratic, capitalist or authoritarian dominance as new technologies facilitate new forms of power (Zuboff, 2019; Srivastava, 2021). In contrast with these dystopian visions, other authors – mostly from engineering – also highlight that the digital transition plays a key role in realizing a large variety of, sometimes seemingly contradictory, objectives such as economic growth, societal stability, poverty relief and nature conservation (for example: Neugebauer, 2019). In the policy debate, there are still high expectations, and the digital transition is seen by the EU as the key to tackling a wide variety of challenges (see: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>).

For some time, there has been a debate about the effectiveness of government rules and regulations to influence the digital transition. The recent edited volume by Moore & Tambini (2021) highlights key issues such as enhancing competition, increasing accountability, safeguarding privacy and protecting democracy. The digital transition is largely shaped by big tech companies and there is much discussion about the external aspect, market regulation and privacy regulation (Wörsdörfer, 2020, Moore & Tambini, 2021; Petropoulos, 2021). Market regulators have been working hard on ensuring proper forms of market oversight in the age of platform organizations and Big Tech (Barroso & Laborda, 2022). Privacy commissioners in many countries play a key role in ensuring that public and private organizations follow privacy rules (Díaz et al., 2022; Lu et al., 2022). For both forms of regulation, however, no studies have systematically mapped the capabilities that are needed to fulfill these roles adequately. Currently there is quite a bit of attention for the regulation of algorithms (Lorenz et al., 2022). The focus, however, is again very much on normative and legal issues and no information is available on these capabilities. The overarching issue, the governance of platforms, is also discussed in fundamental political philosophical terms such as the social contract of platforms with society.

There is broad societal support for government interventions in the continuously changing digital sector. An indication for the broad support is recent hearings in the United States

where both Democrats and Republicans ask hard questions to the tech industry about their contributions to societal welfare and wellbeing. Even for a democratically polarized country such as the US, there is broad consensus that ‘Big Tech has grown too powerful and that action must be taken to address its abuse of power’ (Alford, 2021: 893).

Whereas the sustainability literature emphasizes collaboration, in view of the international competition between big tech companies, there is hardly any global collaboration for the digital transition. The need for international collaboration on digital transition has primarily focused on international collaborations such as the European Union and other regional collaborations. An interesting finding from research into the General Data Protection Regulation is that this had an effect on many other countries. This effect has been referred to as the ‘Brussels Effect’ (Gunst & De Ville, 2021) and describes how laws can have an effect across borders through market mechanisms resulting in the globalization of standards. As such, even if there are no global agreements between national governments, there is still the possibility that global standards can be created.

4.3.2 Organizational capabilities

There is a substantive body of literature on digital government organizations, and this literature is rapidly expanding. Key foundational work includes Snellen & Van de Donk (1998, ‘public administration in an information age’), Fountain (2001, ‘building the virtual state’) & Dunleavy & Margetts (2006, ‘digital era governance’). These analyses all highlight that the use of digital technologies is not only an instrument for government organizations but transforms their very internal nature. Building upon classic work in the field of digital government studies, on more recent literature and on empirical research through expert interviews, Mergel et al. (2019: 12) provide the following comprehensive definition of digital transformation:

‘Digital transformation is a holistic effort to revise core processes and services of government beyond the traditional digitization efforts. It evolves along a continuum of transition from analog to digital to a full stack review of policies, current processes, and user needs and results in a complete revision of the existing and the

creation of new digital services. The outcome of digital transformation efforts focuses among others on the satisfaction of user needs, new forms of service delivery, and the expansion of the user base.'

As the digital transformation is a socio-technical transformation, Mergel et al. (2019) identify a change in culture, skills and mindset as a key condition to make digital transformation last. This is further underpinned by Tangi et al. (2020) as they state that "processes, employees' duties and tasks and information systems are going through a deep transformation" (42) due to digital transformation attempts. Both in the more classic publications on the topic (Snellen & Van de Donk, 1998; Fountain, 2001; Dunleavy et al., 2006) and in recent literature, the need for innovation capability is addressed.

The collaborative capability for the digital transition was already addressed by Homburg's (1999) focus on 'interorganizational information systems' and continues to receive attention through 'e-governance' (Dawes, 2008), 'collaborative e-government' (Ae Chun et al., 2012), and 'open governance' (Meijer et al., 2019). However, the current knowledge regarding the relationship between collaborative governance and digital transition is still limited (Maulana & Decman, 2023).

Regarding operational practices, there is attention for the realization of digital government but also for newer forms such as 'agile government' (Mergel et al., 2018), 'mobile government' (Ntaliani et al., 2008), and 'algorithmic government' (Gupta & Pal, 2021). Moreover, Faro et al. (2022) argue organizations need a hybrid combination of pure bureaucratic as well as network elements to support strategic needs during the digital transition.

4.3.3 Individual capabilities

In terms of the individual capabilities of the digital transition, the actual behavior of civil servants, we could only find one study that focuses on the role of public managers in the implementation of digital transition projects (Kitsios et al., 2023). Kitsios et al. (2023) pay attention to the driving forces behind the transition of public administrations and the

outcomes this produces. Attitude is often, in line with theories on the adoption of innovation, conceptualized as the willingness to use digital technologies. There are some studies available about the attitude of civil servants towards specific forms of digitalization. Alomar (2023) analyzes the determinants of the attitude of civil servants toward using e-public procurement and finds that six factors have a significant impact on the attitude of civil servants, namely perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, training, resources, position of the hierarchy, and clients' attitude. Kleiman et al. (2023) study civil servants' willingness to using open data and find that social influences, performance expectancy, data management knowledge and risks have a significant influence.

Furthermore, there is a longer tradition of research into the digital skills of civil servants (Schuppan, 2010; Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2010; Casalino et al., 2020; Edelman et al., 2023). This research highlights the need for civil servants to understand new technologies, to appreciate its potential and to be able to effectively use new technologies for their work. While much of this work focus on 'digital literacy', there is a growing emphasis on the idea the 'digital literacy' needs to be contextualized and connected to the work of civil servants. Recently, interesting work has been done by Dingelstad et al. (2022) on data competences which emphasizes that digital competences need to be connected to administrative competences. They refer to the requires skills as 'hybrid data competences'. As the digital transition longs for a labor force with digitally skilled workers, Lopes et al. (2023) provide insights into the training of digital skills for workers in the public sector. The findings suggest that the majority of the public sector workers have not participated in training in the digital field in the previous two years, but are willing to participate in these kinds of training to spur the transition. To contribute to further professionalization of civil servants to foster the digital transition, moreover, Storozhev et al. (2023) pay attention to the development of leadership qualities of public servants as a critical factor. Furthermore, Henderikx and Stoffers (2023) exploratively investigate future leadership behaviors and skills of middle managers that are needed during and after the digital transition. Their findings suggest that the importance of soft skills such as empathy, integrity and compassion is increasing.

5. Toward a multilevel framework of government capabilities for the twin transition

5.1. Initial framework on the basis of the narrative review

The three different levels of the twin transition have now been discussed for each body of literature. On the basis of our exploration of the rich literature on the sustainability and digital transition and on the more limited literature on the twin transition, we can now develop a conceptual framework of capabilities for the twin transition at each of these levels. The conceptual understanding consists of an identification of core dimensions for all three levels. Together, this results in a conceptual overview of the government capabilities that are needed for the twin transition.

At the institutional level, the rich literature can be condensed to four main dimensions: regulatory and policy capability, adaptive capability, legitimizing capability and global connective capability. The first dimension, the regulatory and policy capability refers to the key capabilities of government in society: steering societal developments through policy and regulation. These capabilities are highlighted in the literature on the twin transition (Muench et al., 2022). In the literature on sustainability studies, there is much emphasis on the transition management capability (Loorbach, 2010; Braams et al., 2022) and on the ability to formulate missions (Mazzucato, 2018), while the literature on the digital transition, puts an emphasis on the policy capability (Barroso & Laborda, 2022). The regulatory aspect receives less attention in the literature on the twin transition but is highlighted mostly in the literature on the digital transition (Wörsdörfer, 2020, Moore & Tambini, 2021; Petropoulos, 2021). The second dimension is the adaptive capability, which refers to the dynamic aspect of the capabilities, the ability to change in response to new developments. In the literature on the twin transition, Linov et al. (2018) and Muench et al. (2022) pay explicit attention of the need for ‘adaptive governance’ which they define as the adjustment of regulatory rules and practices. The third dimension is the legitimizing capability for the twin transition which broadly means obtaining societal support for the various interventions and action of the twin transition. In the literature on the sustainability transition, there is quite some attention for legitimation as a basis for public support

(Braams et al., 2021) while in the literature on the digital transition this attention is quite limited (Alford, 2021). The fourth dimension is the connective global capability for the twin transition and thus stresses that realizing these transitions requires the ability to work across borders. The literature on the sustainability transition highlights the need of the capability for worldwide collaboration (Kanie & Bierman, 2017; McAllister & Taylor, 2015) and there is also some attention for this international collaboration in the literature on the digital transition (Gunst & De Ville, 2021).

At the organizational level, we can also identify three main dimensions: innovation capability, implementation capability, and collaborative capability. The first dimension is the innovation capability for the twin transition. In the literature on the twin transition this is mentioned by Haley (2017) and Kattel et al. (2022). The second dimension is the implementation capability for the twin transition. Haley (2017) mentions this capability for the twin transition both for the internal and external sustainability transitions. In the literature on the sustainability transition, this capability for organizations in general (e.g. Adams et al., 2014). In the literature on the digital transition the need for a strategy is also emphasized (Sandoval-Almazán et al. (2017). The third dimension is the organizational network capability. This capability is discussed in the literature on the sustainability transition (Pinz et al. (2021) and extensively discussed in the literature on the digital transition (Ae Chun et al., 2012; Meijer et al., 2019; Maulana & Decman, 2023).

At the individual level, we identified four dimensions. First, we identified the skill capability for the twin transition. In this respect, in the literature on the twin transition Cordella et al. (2024) highlight digital skills and these skills are also highlighted in the literature on the digital transition (Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2010). Second, in the literature on the sustainability transition, Braams et al. (2023) highlight organizational astuteness, and a similar point is made by Dingelstad et al. (2022) in the literature on the digital transition. Third, we identified the willingness of employees to work on the twin transition. In the literature on the twin transition, Brenner & Hartl (2021) and Voukkali et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of an open attitude and in the literature on the sustainability transition, there is attention for 'green behavior' (Unsworth et al., 2021) and Green HRM

(Rani & Mishra, 2014). The importance of a positive attitude and realization capability was also emphasized in the literature on the digital transition (Kitsios et al., 2023). Fourthly, we identified the collaborative capability. Schot et al. (2000) highlight the important of collaborative professionalism.

5.2. Explorative test of the initial multilevel framework

The initial framework thus consisted of three levels and in total 11 capabilities within these levels. The idea behind this framework was that these capabilities are needed to realize the twin transition. We did an exploratory test of the value of the framework in two cities in the Netherlands to assess the value of the framework and identify shortcomings. The participants, both from IT and sustainability departments, were asked to highlight specific examples of the various government capabilities and whether they thought their organizations were doing well. We observed how the model helped members of the organization to identify current limitations and formulate actions for strengthening the government capabilities for the twin transition in these two cities.

Overall, we found that the three levels helped the participants to structure the variety of observations they had about the capabilities of the organization. The various dimensions also helped them to identify where they were doing well and where additional action was needed. Both workshops resulted in a list of actions to be taken to strengthen the capabilities for the twin transition.

Participants emphasized the interconnections between the levels and observed that this can be challenging. In one city, a metaphor of a balloon was used. Participants emphasized how the local government organization needs these ‘balloons’, filled up or ‘colored in’ by missions that are established by (e.g.) the city council and the municipal executive. Successful innovations and best practices at the individual level can be ‘attached’ to these balloons to rise. By doing so, such balloons create the opportunity to change the capability of the organization and communicate meaningful results.

This observation was important since, based on the narrative review, we had not focused on the interconnections between the levels and, as far we know, no research has yet been conducted on these interfaces. For this reason, we added the interfaces to our framework. For the interface between the institutional and the organizational levels, we can formulate interfaces in two directions: translating institutional changes to requirements for government organizations, and facilitating contributions from innovative organizations to institutional changes. For the interface between the organizational and the individual capabilities, the importance of translating organizational requirements to individual competences is emphasized, as well as the possibility to build upon changing competences to change organizational conditions.

Another observation concerned two themes that are important at two levels but were not yet identified: leadership and reflection. For leadership, the participants highlighted the importance of persons that can make a difference and can get things moving. For reflection, participants stressed the importance of learning across levels but that this is challenging because of a lack of interaction between different levels. Strengthening these capabilities is an ongoing process that requires organizations to contemplate current practices and identify interventions for improving them, as they had done in the workshop.

5.3. Revised multilevel framework

On the basis of the exploratory empirical test and a new reading of the relevant literature, we revised the initial multilevel framework. Our revised framework consists of the three levels and their components that we had identified on the basis of the narrative literature review, with two important extensions on the basis of the exploratory empirical test.

The first extension concerns the interfaces between the levels which receive limited explicit attention in the literature but were identified as important in the empirical test. For both interfaces, we can formulate interfaces in two directions. For the interface between the institutional and organizations levels, the exploratory test highlighted the need for the capability to translate institutional ambition into organizational requirements and for the

capability to build upon organizational strengths in institutional strategies. In the literature, there was attention for innovation in the sense of creating an institutional context for organizational innovation and innovation as a means to open up the institutional context (Bason, 2010; Bekkers & Tummers, 2018; Mazzucato, 2018; Hekkert et al., 2020; Kattel et al., 2022; Strumińska-Kutra, 2023). For the interface between the organizational and the individual levels, we identified the capability to translate organizational requirements to new sets of individual competences, and the capability to build upon changing individual competences to strengthen organizational conditions. Interesting here is the notion of ‘bureaucratic hackers’ presented by Kattel et al. (2022): individuals need to be able to reshape the organizational competences to realize the twin transition.

The second extension concerns two capabilities that run through the different levels: leadership and reflection. This was pointed out by respondents and participants in both cities. In our initial analysis of the literature, these themes did not emerge but after the empirical research, we went back to the literature. We found that recent papers explicitly highlighted the importance of leadership in the digital transition (Henderikx and Stoffers 2023; Branderhorst and Ruijter 2025). Different forms of political, organizational and individual leadership are needed to work on the required changes at the different levels. As Selznick (1957) has shown, leadership is crucial for changing the fundamental nature of a social system and infuse new values. The second cross-cutting theme is reflection and learning. Loorbach (2009) identifies reflexive capabilities that include monitoring, assessment and evaluation of ongoing policies. Reflexive capabilities, according to Loorbach (2009), need to be integrated and cut through the three levels of the framework. Similar, Kattel et al. (2025) stress that the capabilities need to be dynamic and based on continuous learning.

The resulting revised multilevel framework consists of the initial model and the two extensions. To summarize the main line of argument, a conceptual framework of government capabilities for the twin transition is presented in Figure 1):

INSERT FIGURE 1

Overall, the explorative tests indicates that the framework offers a valuable connection between the literatures on the (ecological) sustainability transition and the digital transition which serves to identify capabilities. In our analysis, we noticed that the literature on the sustainability transition is more mature and theoretically further elaborated. We propose that these differences can be attributed to the more recent attention for the digital transition, and also to the disciplinary differences between science and technology studies and information sciences.

6. Conclusions and research agenda

The argument that we make in this paper is that the twin transition requires governments to build capabilities at multiple levels and to manage the interfaces between them. Based on a narrative review of the literature, we present a multilevel framework which provides an overview of such capabilities. We suggest that the twin transition requires organizations to zoom in on micro-level changes and zoom out to position these changes in the context of organizational and societal changes. This notion forms the basis for the multilevel framework that we present in this paper.

This framework provides a conceptual understanding of the government capabilities that are needed for the twin transition and the explorative test confirms its value for practice. This conceptual understanding has both societal and academic value. The societal value lies in the basis that this overview can provide for organizational assessments of capabilities for the twin transition. The academic value lies in the conceptualization of government capabilities for the twin transition as a basis for more systematic research into both the drivers and implications of government capabilities.

The literature provides surprisingly little specific indications about what will go wrong if certain capabilities are not present. In general, we see two main risks. The first and most prominent risk is that governments will not be able to effectively align the two transitions. This will mean that the possibilities that digital technologies offer to strengthen the

sustainability transition, will not be used. It could even mean that the digital transition runs counter to the sustainability transition when increased use of various digital technologies – for example Artificial Intelligence – would result in enormous use of energy and CO₂-emission. The second risk that is mostly implicitly mentioned in the literature is erosion of democratic legitimacy if technologies are used in ways that run counter to what is seen as desirable and when these usages have been implemented without strong forms of public control (Meijer & Thaens, 2021).

On the basis of our analysis, we highlight the following topics for further research:

1. *Measuring government capabilities for the twin transition.* Our paper provides a conceptual overview but does not indicate how different dimensions of the government capabilities can be measured. Building upon previous work at the different levels, instruments can be developed to measure the capabilities at institutional, organizational and individual levels.
2. *Understanding determinants of government capabilities for the twin transition.* Through comparative research, differences between government capabilities for the twin transition can be mapped and then determinants for these differences (such as democratic system, GDP, leadership, etc.) can be analyzed.
3. *Assessing the impact of the capabilities on the realization of the twin transition.* The impact of the competences on the realization of the twin transition can be analyzed to obtain an understanding of which types of competences are crucial and which types of competences work best in different contexts. The impact of these capabilities on perceived government legitimacy also needs to be investigated.
4. *Methods for strengthening the government capabilities for the twin transition.* In addition to an understanding of the determinants, methods for strengthening these capabilities through smart allocation of funding, collaborative networks, international learning, etc., can be explored and assessed.
5. *Extending our understanding of government capabilities to social and economic sustainability.* This paper follows the European Union's narrower focus on ecological sustainability but further academic work needs to broaden this

understanding to include also social and economic sustainability.

6. *Extending our understanding of the interfaces and cross-cutting dimensions.* The empirical exploration of the framework resulted in the identification of these dimensions, which is an important addition to the literature. Further research is needed to provide an in-depth understanding of these elements.

Future research can take a conventional approach but, in view of the urgency of these issues, most importantly global warming, an argument can be made for more societally engaged research (Vaughn, 2025). An engaged researcher that aims to make concrete contributions to the different challenges facing governments. Researchers can provide training and evaluate how this training contributes to the individual capability; they can give organizational or government advice and evaluate how this impacts organizational and institutional capabilities. Researchers can work in international networks to facilitates the interchange of knowledge between countries and contribute to global competences for the twin transition. We hope that the framework we provided in this paper will help to facilitate an international research agenda so that we as a research community can contribute to the urgent actions that are needed for the twin transition.

The model in this paper was specifically developed for the twin transition. At the same time, its conceptualization of government capability can possibly also be applied to other socio-technical challenges. As such, it connects to broader debates about the need for government innovation as a basis for tackling societal challenges (Bason, 2010; Mazzucato, 2018; Hekkert et al., 2020). Subsequent work on other socio-technical challenges such as the energy, social and economic transitions is needed to explore whether the multilevel framework can indeed be regarded as a general framework for socio-technical challenges.

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Table 1: Framework for identifying government capabilities for the twin transition

Types of capabilities	Description capability
<i>Institutional</i>	The ability of to formulate a legitimate institutional strategy, a long-term vision, policy goals and norms regarding the twin transition
<i>Organizational</i>	The ability to develop and implement programs, (network) arrangements and (collaborative) structures (such as roles and responsibilities, budgeting, procurement, human resource management, regulations) that support the twin transition
<i>Individual</i>	The ability to translate the strategy and tactics into concrete innovative actions such as experimentation, best practices, learning by doing to execute tasks in projects and programs regarding the twin transition

Figure 1: Government capabilities for the twin transition

